

Study of the stereochemistry of new tetranortriterpenoids isolated from root-wood of *Chisocheton paniculatus* Hiern (Meliaceae)^{†#}

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The structures and stereochemistry of the new compounds arunachalin, paniculatin B, paniculatin C, panicualtin D, paniculatin G and paniculatin H, isolated from the root-wood of *Chisocheton paniculatus* Hiern (Meliaceae) have been determined on the basis of chemical transformations and spectral data.

In our continuing studies^{1,2} on the Meliaceae of the NER of India we have investigated the root-wood of *Chisocheton paniculatus*, a member of the Meliaceae from this region. The plant material was collected from tropical evergreen forest of Namsai, Chessa from Arunachal Pradesh, India.

Limonoids have attracted much attention because of the marked insect antifeedant and growth regulating, antifungal activity of azadirachtin and related limonoids isolated from the neem tree and also of few limonoids isolated from the fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus* Hiern²⁻⁴. More recently limonoids have shown anticarcinogenic and antitumourigenic activities^{4a-d}. More than 400 limonoids and protolimonoids have been isolated and characterized from natural sources and in almost all cases correct α -orientation¹ at C-7 is depicted. However two early examples of β -orientation have also been reported in the literature^{5,6}.

Petroleum ether extract of powdered root-wood yielded a complex mixture of several compounds. After careful chromatographic separation and crystallization one compound was isolated (tlc) and assigned the structure and named arunachalin (1). The isolation, identification of known compounds paniculatin, β -sitosterol and structure elucidation of new compounds, paniculatin B (5), paniculatin C (11), panicualtin D (18), paniculatin G and paniculatin H, isolated from the root-wood of *C. paniculatus* Hiern have been reported in the previous communications⁷. But the stereochemistry of these compounds were not determined totally. In this communication we report the stereochemistry of the isolated new compounds.

High resolution ¹H NMR spectrum of arunachalin (1) shows signals of five quaternary methyls at δ 0.88, 1.02 (each 3H, s), 1.05 (6H, s) and two epoxy methyls at 1.32 (6H, s). Also a triplet at δ 2.21 and a doublet at 2.74 justify an environment similar to ring-D of phebaloparvilactone⁸.

The presence of a six-proton singlet at δ 1.32 and a doublet at 2.86 advocates of an α -oxirane ring in the side-chain which is also supported by an ion peak at m/z 71 (20%). A broad singlet at δ 5.32, integrated to one proton, justifies the presence of a hydroxyl function at C-21 (Table 1). The ¹H NMR spectrum of 1 is very much similar to cneorin-NP₃₈ (2)⁶, except that 1 exhibited one additional double bond at $\Delta^{9(11)}$. Other spectral properties (¹³C NMR, Table 1) of compound 1 when compared with those reported for melianone⁹ and 21-*O*-acetyltoosendantriol (4)¹⁰, reveal 1 to be an apo-tirucallane type triterpene. To ascertain the stereochemistry of 1, it was hydrogenated to give compound 3, and the ¹³C NMR data were compared with those of compound 4, the stereochemistry of which was fixed through X-ray crystallographic studies¹⁰.

- 1
2 9(11)-dihydro
3 9(11)-dihydro-7,8-*trans*-epoxide

The chemical shifts for the carbons on the side-chain as well as those related carbons coincide very closely with those of compounds 1, 3 and 4, indicating that these compounds have the same steric structures. These observations led us to define the complete stereostructure of arunachalin as structure 1.

[†]Dedicated with profound respect and gratitude to Professor D. Nasipuri, an outstanding organic chemist, on his 75th. birth anniversary.

[#]Part II of the Series : New protolimonoids and limonoids. For Part I see Ref. 1.

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz) data for compounds 1, 4, 5, 11, 13, 17, 18 and 20*

Position	Groups	1	4	5	11	13	17	18	20
1	CH ₂	33.04	32.60	33.04	33.12	33.2	158.5	33.18	33.2
2	CH ₂	22.64	25.11	22.64	22.68	22.8	126.9	22.72	22.7
3	C	77.99	76.17	77.99	78.05	78.1	204.2	78.07	78.1
4	C	36.04	37.08	36.04	36.08	36.2	44.5	36.12	36.1
5	CH	41.74	40.55	41.74	41.78	41.9	43.7	41.81	41.8
6	CH ₂	23.47	23.85	23.47	23.55	23.6	23.9	23.56	23.6
7	CH	72.08	72.35	72.08	72.35	72.5	74.1	72.18	72.2
8	C/CH	44.30	44.49	44.30	44.36	44.5	44.5	44.38	44.3
9	C/CH	41.44	41.60	41.44	41.62	41.7	45.2	41.55	41.5
10	C	37.48	37.79	37.48	37.44	37.5	42.0	37.57	37.6
11	CH/CH ₂	118.45	16.30	16.17	16.34	16.4	70.6	16.21	16.3
12	CH ₂	32.87	32.62	32.87	34.03	34.1	42.1	33.18	33.2
13	C	46.59	46.73	46.59	46.60	46.7	45.6	46.57	46.6
14	C	36.75	162.37	162.27	162.29	162.4	159.5	162.14	162.1
15	CH/CH ₂	33.70	119.25	119.42	119.66	119.8	119.1	119.56	119.6
16	CH ₂	34.92	35.09	34.92	34.72	34.8	35.9	34.91	35.0
17	CH	52.56	52.64	52.56	52.14	52.5	52.7	52.67	52.6
18	CH ₃	20.30	19.59	20.30	21.67	19.2	20.1	21.73	
19	CH ₃	20.52	15.23	19.11	15.10	15.2	19.8	15.10	
20	CH	45.32	44.32	45.32	35.72	35.9	46.1	44.72	44.7
21	CH	97.43	96.77	97.43	70.02	70.1	97.6	96.69	96.5
22	CH ₂	31.25	31.48	31.25	36.26	36.4	31.7	30.07	30.3
23	CH	78.22	79.95	77.22	86.44	86.5	78.9	75.53	78.4
24	CH	67.58	66.79	67.58	64.36	64.5	68.0	75.05	75.2
25	C	57.45	57.11	57.45	73.94	74.1	57.6	73.59	73.7
26	CH ₃	27.77	28.07	27.77	28.38	28.5	25.3	27.79	27.8
27	CH ₃	21.67	22.14	21.67	23.97	21.8	20.5	27.53	27.6
28	CH ₃	26.30	24.94	24.85	27.50	27.6	26.3	26.66	26.6
29	CH ₃	21.50	27.91	25.50	27.82	27.9	21.5	26.42	26.6
30	CH ₃	30.30	19.59	19.69	19.13	19.2	30.3	19.85	19.7

*In CDCl₃.

The ^1H nmr spectrum of paniculatin B (5) showed signals due to seven tertiary methyls, one acetoxy group, an olefinic proton at δ 5.49, two oxymethine protons at 4.66 and 3.90 and one distinct epoxymethine proton at 2.85. Comparison of these data with several known molecules like melianol, melianone and glabretal etc. suggests an apotirucallol skeleton leading to structure 5. The stereochemistry of 5 was assigned on the basis of chemical transformations to known compounds and comparison of ^{13}C nmr spectral data with those of known molecules. Acetylation of 5 with Ac₂O and pyridine furnished a diacetate (7) which was identical with the acetate derivative of 21-*O*-acetyltoosendantriol (4), a known molecule¹⁰. On hydrolysis, compound 5 gave a triol (6). Chromium trioxide oxidation (Sarett

oxidation) of paniculatin B (5) furnished the corresponding monoketone (8) smoothly. However, oxidation with Jones' reagent led to the formation of five products which on separation by preparative tlc isolated only two products, the structures of which were deduced as 9 and 10 respectively. These compounds may be formed by opening of the epoxide ring and oxidation in the side-chain. Similar alternative substituted butenolide is reported from the seed extract of this species^{11,12}. Based on a detailed comparison of spectral data (IR, MS, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, Table 1) of compound 5 with those of 4, it was inferred that the proper stereostructure for paniculatin B was 5. This inferred structure (5) was further confirmed by studying the ^{13}C NMR spectra. All carbons closely coincided with those of 4 in both chemical

shifts and multiplicities, corroborating that **4** and **5** have the same stereostructure. The side-chain structure of **5** was deduced as follows. Atoms C-24 and C-25 resonated at δ_c 67.58 and 57.45 respectively, chemical shifts of which are in agreement with those (C-24, δ_c 66.79 and C-25 δ_c 57.11 respectively) of the corresponding carbons reported^{10a} for compound **4**, with a side-chain including epoxide system. Thus the structure of paniculatin B is now defined as **5**.

	R ¹	R ²	R ³
4	H	H	Ac
5	H	Ac	H
6	H	H	H
7	Ac	Ac	Ac

The spectroscopic properties of paniculatin C revealed the presence of seven tertiary methyl groups, a trisubstituted double bond, one tertiary and two secondary hydroxy groups, a secondary acetate, and a cyclic ether. The nature of the side-chain of **11** was readily deduced from the similarity of the appropriate data, especially the H-24 doublet (J 9 Hz) at δ 2.90 with those recorded for grandifoliolenone, another known¹³ compound and the closely related sapelin D (**13**)^{13,14}. The remaining information suggested an apotirucallol skeleton with 3 α -hydroxy and 7 α -acetoxy group and led to structure **11** for paniculatin C. This was confirmed by chemical transformations to known compounds and comparison of the spectral data (¹³C NMR).

To start with, paniculatin C (**11**) was acetylated to give the triacetate (**12**) and a diacetate where 3 α -hydroxy remained intact. On hydrolysis, paniculatin C (**11**) was converted to sapelin D (**13**), a known compound and sapelin D

	R ¹	R ²	R ³
11	H	Ac	H
12	Ac	Ac	Ac
13	H	H	H
14	3,7,23-triketo deriv. of 13		
15	3,7-diketo deriv. of 13		
16	3,23-diketo deriv. of 11		
Known	3-Acetyl deriv. of 13		

triacetate¹³ was also identical with the triacetate (**12**) obtained from **11**. The hydrolysed product **13** (sapelin D) renders the corresponding 3,23-diketone (**15**) on Sarett oxidation and the 3,7,23-triketone (**14**) on Jones oxidation, a known triketone obtained from sapelin D¹³. On the other hand, when paniculatin C (**11**) was oxidised directly with Jones reagent it gave a mixture of products, difficult to isolate. Based on these detailed information and comparison of spectral data (IR, MS, ¹H NMR) of **11** and **13**, it was inferred that structure **11** is the correct structure for paniculatin C. This structure was further confirmed through ¹³C NMR study (Table 1). All the carbons of **11** closely coincide with those of **13** in both chemical shifts and multiplicities. Further, the stereo-structure **11** was confirmed through ¹³C DEPT and homonuclear HHCOSY experiment for paniculatin C (**11**). Thus the complete structure of paniculatin C is settled as **11**.

Paniculatin D (**18**) is a tetrahydroxy, non-furanoid apotirucallane derivative in which epoxide is opened in a *cis* manner. It has a α -orientated oxygen function (OAc) at C-7 similar to paniculatin C (**11**) already described. The absence of epoxide is revealed by the lack of a doublet at δ 2.85 (H-24) and a singlet at 1.32 (6H) in the ¹H NMR spectrum. However, the presence of a triplet at δ 4.54 and a broad singlet at 3.16 is attributed to two hydroxyl groups at C-24 and C-25 respectively. ¹³C NMR spectrum of paniculatin D (**18**) is very similar to that of **20**, a known compound¹¹. The stereochemistry of the two hydroxyl groups are *cis* to each other which is supported by the formation of an acetonide (**22**) with dry acetone in presence of anhydrous copper sulphate at room temperature. To settle the stereo-

chemistry of C-24 and C-25, paniculatin D (**18**) was hydrolysed and acetylated to get the known compounds **19** and **21** with defined stereochemistry. Thus the complete structure of paniculatin D is settled as **18**.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of paniculatin G is similar to paniculatin B (**5**) except that the former displays almost all signals downfield by about 0.02 ppm. The ^{13}C NMR dif-

fering hydroxyl function at C-3, is easier than that of a boat conformation, leading to a more stable ion at m/z 354 (27.7%) in compound **5**. This fact together with the absence of other corresponding ion peaks from the compound paniculatin G led us to conclude that this compound is conformational isomer of paniculatin B (**5**) only.

Paniculatin H is a crystalline solid but very unstable in

fers only in terms of relative intensities of the signals. No specific change other than relative intensities, is observed in DEPT experiment. It was observed that molecules of this series are very sensitive towards energy change. So this advantage was taken and studied the mass fragmentation pattern of both the compounds in higher energy (70 eV). The EIMS of both the compounds gave m/z 372 (M^+ -side-chain)⁺ but unique and informative changes were observed in both the spectra. The number of ions generated for paniculatin B (**5**) was 137 whereas for paniculatin G, it was 187. The base peaks for **5** was recorded at m/z 43 (100%). Remarkable features were obtained comparing the fragmentation pattern in between mass number 279 and 372 which may be taken as finger print zone for ring A and ring B of this series.

The above data clearly show that ion peaks pertaining to changes to ring A and ring B are missing in paniculatin G. This shows that the two molecules differ in ring-A. Moreover, loss of water molecule from a chair conformation, hav-

ing solvent like chloroform. There is no signal for epoxide or six-membered heterocyclic ring in its ^1H NMR spectrum. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum indicates that it is an epimeric mixture and consists of a five-membered heterocyclic ring in the side-chain similar to paniculatin D (**18**).

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries on a Buchi 510 apparatus and are uncorrected. Optical rotation was taken on a Optical activity polarimeter (AA1000). UV (MeOH) spectra were recorded on Hitachi 320 and Jasco 7800 spectrophotometers, IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer, NMR spectra on Varian EM-390 and Bruker WM-400 spectrometers using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on Jeol-300 or INCOS 50 GC/MS/DS spectrometer. Tlc and preparative tlc were performed on Si-gel G (E. Merck) and column chromatography on Si-gel (B.D.H., 60–120 mesh). Arunachalin (**1**), paniculatin (**3**), paniculatin B (**4**), paniculatin C (**5**), paniculatin D (**6**),

paniculatin G and paniculatin H were isolated from the root-wood of *C. paniculatus* Hiern and the part structures elucidated as per the procedure reported in the earlier communication⁷.

Arunachalin (1) : White crystalline solid (C₆H₆ : MeOH, 9 : 1, plates), m.p. 216–217°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –12° (*c* 2.0, CHCl₃); λ_{\max} 216, 219 and 221 nm ($\epsilon = 10000$); ν_{\max} 3600–3200, 1712, 1450, 1370, 1090, 810 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.88, 1.02, 1.05 (6H), 1.12 and 1.32 (6H, six CH₃), 2.12 (H-5), 2.78 (d, *J* 6 Hz, H-7), 5.36 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-12), 2.21 (t, *J* 8 Hz, H-17), 2.74 (d, *J* 5 Hz, H-20), 5.32 (H-21), 3.9 (s, H-23), 2.86 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-24); EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 483 [M-1]⁺, 455, 325 (6) [M-side-chain-2H]⁺, 271 (10) [M-side-chain-C₆H₅-CH₂]⁺, 109, 69 (100); calcd. for C₃₀H₄₄O₅.

Paniculatin B (5) : Crystalline solid (MeOH), m.p. 241–243°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –1.609° (*c* 2.0, CHCl₃); λ_{\max} 203 nm; ν_{\max} 3535–3300, 1728, 1385, 1370, 1240, 1180, 1060, 870 cm⁻¹; ¹³C NMR vide Table 1; EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 512 [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 372 (59) [M⁺-side-chain]⁺, 354 (27.7) [372-H₂O]⁺, 312 (9.1) [372-AcOH]⁺, 294 (13.6) [312-H₂O]⁺, 279 (25.2) [294-CH₃]⁺; calcd. for C₃₂H₅₀O₆.

Paniculatin C (11) : Crystalline solid (MeOH), m.p. 200–202°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –2.59° (*c* 4.0, CHCl₃); λ_{\max} 205 nm; ν_{\max} 3533, 3371, 1725, 1382, 1372, 1248, 1175, 1072, 824, 732 cm⁻¹; ¹³C nmr vide Table 1; EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 514 (17.9) [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 475 (14.9), 396 (10.8), 373 (17.0) [M⁺-side-chain+1]⁺, 372 (40.9) [M⁺-side-chain]⁺, 354 (18.7), 160 (31) [side-chain]⁺; calcd. for C₃₂H₅₂O₆.

Paniculatin D (18) : Crystalline solid (MeOH), m.p. 148–151°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –2.59° (*c* 4.0, CHCl₃); λ_{\max} 205 nm; ν_{\max} 3697–3424, 1727, 1460, 1375, 1244, 1095, 872, 807 cm⁻¹; ¹³C NMR vide Table 1; EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 548 (17.9) [M⁺], 470 (14.0), 373 (12.6) [M⁺-side-chain+1]⁺, 372 (26.5) [M⁺-side-chain]⁺, 354 (13.1), 175 (14.1) [side-chain-1]⁺; 160 (31) [side-chain]⁺; calcd. for C₃₂H₅₂O₇.

Paniculatin G : Crystalline solid (EtOH, plates), m.p. 220–222°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –2.59° (*c* 4.0, CHCl₃); λ_{\max} 205 nm; ν_{\max} 3697–3424, 1727, 1460, 1375, 1244, 1095, 872, 810 cm⁻¹; EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 512 (17.9) [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 373 (6.7), 372 (21.2) [M⁺-side-chain]⁺, 354 (5.70) [372-H₂O], 187 (10.1), 175 (10.0), 173 (12.0), 160 (14.8), 159 (19.0), 135 (20.0), 83 (100); calcd. for C₃₂H₅₀O₆.

Paniculatin H : Crystalline solid (MeOH), m.p. 122–125°; EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 614 [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 576, 518, 502, 470, 464, 454, 426, 372, 330, 219 (100); unstable and difficult to characterize.

Hydrogenation of arunachalin (1) : In a glass hydrogenation apparatus were placed a solution of compound **1** (40 mg) in methanol (50 ml) and palladium in charcoal (10%, 50 mg) as catalyst. The vessel was closed, air removed and hydrogen gas introduced until a pressure of 20 lbs/sq. in was attained. The reaction was started by shaking the apparatus which continued for 5 h. The catalyst was then filtered and the solvent removed to give a solid which was crystallized from ethanol to give a crystalline product (30 mg), characterized as **3**, m.p. 230°; *m/z* 486 M⁺, 472, 430, 332, 147, 93 and 57 (100%). In the ¹H NMR spectrum, the doublet at δ 5.36 (due to the olefinic proton at C-11) was absent in the product **3**. Other peaks were similar to that of compound **1**.

Hydrolysis of paniculatin B (5) : A mixture of **5** (50 mg) and 5% methanolic KOH was stirred for 4 h and then refluxed for 2 h on a water-bath. The resultant mixture showed two new spots in tlc along with that of **5**. The mixture was diluted with water (30 ml) and kept overnight, filtered, residue washed with water, and purified by preparative tlc (Bz-EtO Ac :: 1 : 1) to obtain **6** (10 mg), m.p. 290°; *m/z* 488 M⁺, 470, 455, 428, 413, 330, 315, 297, 279, 213, 1598, 145, 131, 121, 107, 91, 69, 55 (100%).

Acetylation of paniculatin B (5) : To a solution of **5** (30 mg) in pyridine (1 ml) was added Ac₂O (1.5 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand for 6 h. It was then kept in refrigerator overnight after adding water (20 ml). The solid obtained after filtration was washed with water (5 × 20 ml) and purified by preparative tlc (C₆H₆) to obtain **7** (20 mg); ν_{\max} (CCl₄) 1735, 1445, 1390, 1385, 1208, 1095, 1055, 910, 786, 760 cm⁻¹; *m/z* (70 eV) 554 [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 512, 494, 479, 434, 417, 359, 357, 264, 219, 199, 121, 107, 95, 69 (100%), 55. In the ¹H NMR there were three acetyl signals.

Oxidation of paniculatin B (5) with chromium trioxide in pyridine (Sarett oxidation) : CrO₃ (50 mg) was added in portions with stirring to an ice-cold solution of paniculatin B (50 mg) in dry pyridine (2 ml) during 45 min and kept overnight. The reaction mixture was then poured in water (50 ml) and extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 20 ml). Normal work-up of the organic layer afforded a gummy residue which was chromatographed over silica-gel. The C₆H₆ elute yielded **8** (12 mg) as gum : ν_{\max} 1728, 1710, 1160, 1140, 812 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 510 [M⁺], 495, 465, 449, 405, 391, 370, 352, 310, 218, 203, 149, 111, 97, 71, 69, 57 (100%), 55.

Oxidation of paniculatin B (5) with Jones reagent : Paniculatin B (**5**; 20 mg) in acetone (3 ml) was treated with

Jones reagent (3 drops) at 0°. The crude product was chromatographed on preparative tlc (C₆H₆-EtOAc, 4 : 1) which furnished five products of which two were characterized as **9** and **10** from the spectral information : *m/z* 9 542 M⁺, 508, 448, 423, 397, 379, 370, 278, 267, 249, 203, 173, 159, 121 (100%), 105, 91, 69, 55; **10** *m/z* 544 M⁺, 529, 512, 496, 437, 372, 354, 339, 315, 279, 201, 172, 159, 135, 121, 105, 91, 81, 69, 55 (100%).

Hydrolysis of paniculatin C (11) : A solution of **11** (210 mg) in 5% methanolic KOH (25 ml) was stirred for 32 h and then refluxed for 16 h on a water-bath. To it 5% HCl (10 ml) was added and then extracted with CHCl₃. The gummy substance was dissolved in C₆H₆ from which **13** (95 mg) was crystallized, m.p. 239–243° (lit.¹⁴ 243–244°); [α]_D -0.195 (*c* 1.0, CH₃OH); ¹H NMR (90 MHz) and ir spectra of this compound were comparable to sapelin D¹⁴.

Acetylation of paniculatin C (11) : To a solution of paniculatin diacetate (100 mg, prepared first) in pyridine (2 ml) was added Ac₂O (2 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand for 12 h. It was then kept in a refrigerator overnight after adding water (20 ml). The solid obtained after filtration was washed with water (5×20 ml) and purified by preparative tlc (C₆H₆) to obtain quantitative yield of triacetate **12**, m.p. 158–160°; [α]_D -0.463 (*c* 1.0, CHCl₃); *v*_{max} (CCl₄) 3485, 2944, 2868, 1727, 1459, 1453, 1446, 1372, 1247, 1211, 1175, 1037, 979, 946, 814 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.76, 0.90, 0.93, 1.02, 1.15, 1.17, 1.20 (all CH₃), 1.98, 2.04 and 2.09 (OAc), 5.16 (br, s, H-3), 2.68 (br s, H-5), 4.70 (br s, H-7), 5.28 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-15), 3.56, 4.02 (Abq, *J* 12 Hz, 2H-21), 4.96 (m, H-23), 3.16 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-24); GC/MS (70 eV) *m/z* 617 [M⁺-1]⁺, 598 [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 556, 538, 523, 512, 498, 481, 438, 414, 361, 354, 279, 197, 187, 161, 135, 120, 107, 95, 69, 59 (100%), 55.

Oxidation of paniculatin C (11) with chromium trioxide in pyridine (Sarett oxidation) : Compound **11** (20 mg) was oxidized with CrO₃ in pyridine in usual procedure which gave diketone **16** (5 mg) when worked up within 2 h : *v*_{max} (CCl₄) 3430, 2930, 2868, 1725, 1711, 1373, 1243, 1173, 1110, 1030, 790. In ¹H NMR spectrum, signals due to acetate function was observed.

Oxidation of 13 with chromium trioxide in pyridine (Sarett oxidation) : To compound **13** (50 mg) dissolved in dry pyridine (3 ml) was added a solution of CrO₃ (50 mg) in pyridine (3 ml) at ice-temperature for a period of 20 min. The mixture was stirred for 1 h and finally extracted with CHCl₃ after adding water (50 ml). The gummy product ob-

tained by evaporating CHCl₃ was chromatographed on silica-gel. The C₆H₆ : EtOAc elute (4 : 1) resulted **15** (15 mg) as gum : GC/MS (70 eV) 468 [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 453 [M⁺-H₂O-CH₃]⁺, 435 [M⁺-2H₂O-CH₃]⁺, 428, 397, 353, 339, 328, 326, 283, 269, 254, 247, 234, 173, 159, 147, 133, 81, 69, 59 (100%), 55.

Oxidation of 13 with Jones reagent : Compound **13** (20 mg) dissolved in acetone (5 ml) and cooled to 0°, was treated with Jones reagent (3–4 drops). The crude product was chromatographed through a small column and purified on preparative tlc (C₆H₆ : EtOAc :: 4 : 1) to furnish triketone **14** (5 mg), m.p. 173–175° (lit.^{13,14} 175–177°); GC/MS (70 eV) *m/z* 466 [M⁺-H₂O]⁺, 426, 411, 393, 381, 327, 326, 313, 295, 283, 271, 259, 247, 234, 171, 159, 147, 133, 119, 107, 91, 81, 69, 55 (100%).

Preparation of 13 from 12 : A solution of sapelin D triacetate (**12**; 20 mg) in 5% methanolic KOH (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 24 h. The product obtained by usual work up and after crystallization from CHCl₃ gave sapelin D (10 mg), m.p. 242–244°, identical in all respect with the compound obtained from the hydrolysis of paniculatin C (**13**).

Hydrolysis of paniculatin D (18) : A mixture of **18** (55 mg) and 5% methanolic KOH (10 ml) was stirred for 24 h. The resultant mixture was diluted with water (30 ml), neutralized by 5% HCl before extracting in CH₂Cl₂, washed with cold water and dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. The gummy substance obtained on removing the solvent under reduced pressure showed the absence of OAc group in the ¹H NMR spectrum (90 MHz, CDCl₃) but GC/MS showed the presence of impurities. The product was purified by preparative tlc (Bz-EtOAc :: 1 : 1) to obtain **19** (30 mg), m.p. 270°; *v*_{max} 3655, 3460, 3435, 3106, 2940, 2868, 1720, 1462, 1385, 1302, 1154, 1095, 1035, 999.

Acetylation of paniculatin D (18) : To a solution of **18** (55 mg) in pyridine (1 ml) was added of Ac₂O (1.5 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand for 6 h and then kept overnight. After adding water (20 ml) the solid obtained was washed with water (5×20 ml) and purified by preparative tlc (C₆H₆) to obtain the triacetate (**21**; 20 mg). ¹H NMR spectrum (90 MHz, CDCl₃) showed the presence of OAc peaks at δ 1.90, 2.25 and 2.40; *v*_{max} (CCl₄) 3518, 3425, 2940, 2872, 1735, 1725, 1462, 1446, 1372, 1244, 1091, 1068, 1035, 760 cm⁻¹.

Preparation of paniculatin D acetone (22) : Pure paniculatin D (**18**; 5 mg) was mixed with anhyd. CuSO₄ (20 mg) taken in dry CH₃COCH₃ (5 ml). The reaction mix-

ture was sealed in a tube and was worked up after seven days. Acetonide **22** was obtained as gum : m/z 590 $[M^+ - 2H]^+$, 573 $[M^+ - CH_3]^+$, 555 $[M^+ - H_2O - CH_3]^+$, 512, 441, 381, 372 $[M^+ - \text{side-chain}]^+$, 354, 345, 312, 279, 215, 187, 173, 159, 145, 129, 121, 69, 59 (100%), 55.

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